

Towards Predicting Pedestrian Paths: Identifying Surroundings from Monocular Video

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Abstract. Pedestrian behavior is an essential subject of study when developing or enhancing urban infrastructure. However, most behavior elicitation techniques are inherently bound to be biased by either the observer, the subject, or the environment. The SIMUSAFE project aims at collecting road users' behavioral data in naturalistic and realistic scenarios to produce more accurate decision-making models. Using video captured from a monocular camera worn by a pedestrian, we employ machine learning and computer vision techniques to identify areas of interest surrounding a pedestrian. Namely, we use object detection and depth estimation to generate a map of obstacles that may influence the pedestrian's actions. Our methods have shown to be successful in detecting free and occupied areas from monocular video.

Keywords: Pedestrian behavior · Machine learning · Computer vision

1 Introduction

Understanding pedestrian behavior is vital to study and develop transportation and mobility systems. The actions each pedestrian performs have an impact on the actions of other pedestrians and drivers. Therefore, researchers and engineers must account for the causes and consequences of these actions to build improved infrastructure.

Generally, researchers examine human response by putting subjects in a controlled environment, observing their behavior, or allowing the subjects to describe their behavior in unconfined environments. However, the data retrieved is likely to be biased. On the one hand, the observer's point of view will never be the same as the subject's. On the other hand, it is hard for a subject to clearly explain what he or she has experienced during the experiment.

The SIMUSAFE¹ project collects video and position data from human pedestrians and drivers acting in real-life scenarios, intending to improve driving and

¹ <http://simusafe.eu/>

traffic simulators’ technology by enhancing how simulators assess risk perception and decision making of road users. Our global aim is to use the collected data, which is independent of the observer’s or subject’s bias, to understand how what a pedestrian observes influences its locomotion and body movement.

In this paper, we focus on the particular issue of extracting relevant environment information from the gathered data. More specifically, we present a methodology for identifying areas of interest surrounding pedestrians, which may affect their decision-making, from video captured by a monocular smart-glass camera worn by pedestrians in their daily commutes.

Our approach is innovative in two ways: we study data gathered in a naturalistic setting, where the pedestrians are performing their daily routines, and we generate an environment representation from the pedestrian’s point of view, which can provide more insight than an outside perspective.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 contains an overview of the related work and gap analysis; Section 3 details the method we applied for identifying a pedestrian’s surroundings and shows the results of applying it to our data; Section 4 exposes the conclusions as well as future work.

2 Related Work

The taxonomy of pedestrian behavior prediction studies introduced by Ridet *et al.* [9] categorizes studies according to input data. One category encompasses studies that focus on predicting pedestrian behavior by evaluating how pedestrians’ surroundings influence their actions. We consider our work to belong to this category and review related works that fit the same class.

From video data of a real crosswalk, Suh *et al.* [10] observed that in that particular crosswalk, most pedestrians had a gap-seeking behavior, crossing when a gap between vehicles is available, regardless of the pedestrian crossing signal indication. The researchers argue that models that do not take this behavior into account may be overestimating the average pedestrian waiting time in a crosswalk. Using statistics from the gathered data, Suh *et al.* have generated a model that more closely resembles the waiting times observed in the studied situation. However, it did not consider scenarios where crosswalks do not have pedestrian signals.

Rasouli *et al.* [7] studied pedestrian crossing behavior from the perspective of an autonomous vehicle. They developed an annotated dataset from real video data that contains information about the environment (e.g., street width, weather) and the actions taken by the pedestrian (e.g., walking, looking, gestures), to improve behavior prediction in crossings with and without pedestrian signals.

Another work by Bock *et al.* [1] involves a system that continuously improves its prediction of pedestrian trajectories at an intersection. The system uses global navigation satellite systems to track pedestrians’ positions and an array of other devices, including cameras mounted on vehicles, to gather information about the environment.

From our literature review, we found a lack of studies that consider the environment’s characteristics from the pedestrian’s point of view. We intend to contribute to the understanding of pedestrian behavior by describing the environment as a pedestrian observes it. Specifically, we wish to extract relevant parts of the pedestrians’ surroundings that might affect their decision making from video captured with the monocular camera of smart-glasses that pedestrians wore on their daily commutes.

3 Identifying Surroundings from Monocular Video

Through the use of smart glasses to record pedestrian behavior, we have access to data that reliably describes part of the pedestrians’ actual behavior in their regular commutes, while avoiding the cost of setting up a simulation environment. Plus, we have access to much of the information sensed by the pedestrian. While the camera does not record sound nor captures the same field of view as the human eye, it shows most of the surroundings the pedestrian observes at a given point in time.

Considering the pedestrian as an agent in a multi-agent system, the set of obstacles, vehicles, and other nearby pedestrians represents the *environment* at a given point in time, and the pedestrian’s body movement represents its *action*. The smart glasses possess a monocular camera that captures images at fixed frame-rate of 30 Hz with 1920 pixels of width and 1080 pixels of height (full-HD resolution). Therefore, we can extract information about the environment 30 times in a second. To do so, we try to map relevant parts of the environment using two techniques: object detection and depth estimation.

3.1 Object Detection

To detect objects in an image, we trained a neural network using YOLO [8] on the KITTI dataset [2]. The network can detect entities such as cars, people, and traffic signs. Because the head of a pedestrian is continually moving, the recorded video is very unsteady. To facilitate object detection, we stabilize the video without re-scaling. The object detection network determines the bounding box of a detected object and labels it with the most likely class. For each frame, we store information about all the detected objects. Let V represent a video, which is a set of frames. We represent a frame as shown in Equation 1, where *frame_number* is the index of the frame in the video (the first frame of a video will have *frame_number* = 1), t is the frame’s timestamp in seconds and *Context* is the set of detected objects.

$$frame = \{frame_number, t, Context\} \tag{1}$$

We represent each *object* \in *Context* as shown in Equation 2, where *class* is the class to which the object belongs (which can be “car”, “person” or “traffic sign”), (x_{min}, y_{min}) is the lower-left corner and (x_{max}, y_{max}) is the upper-right corner of the object’s bounding box in pixels.

$$object = \{class, x_{min}, y_{min}, x_{max}, y_{max}\} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Depth Estimation

While the object detection neural network achieves satisfactory results, it does not detect all objects in the frame. Being unable to identify objects nearby, which can be obstacles in the pedestrian’s path, is very troublesome. To solve this issue, we also perform a depth estimation for each pixel in a frame to detect other obstacles. Because the video is captured from a monocular camera, we cannot apply techniques available in stereo setups to calculate depth. Therefore, we trained a neural network using the MonoDepth [5] algorithm on the Karlsruhe dataset [3, 4], which contains stereo video recorded from a moving vehicle. For each left frame in the stereo camera video, the neural network estimates its disparity map, i.e., how much each pixel of the frame must shift to achieve the image from the right camera. While the neural network requires the left and right frame for training, it only requires one frame as input for inference. Hence, we feed our monocular video frames to the neural network and obtain disparity values for each pixel. Let b be the baseline in meters of a stereo camera setup, f the focal length of both cameras in pixels, z the depth of an object in meters, and d the disparity in pixels of the object. The relation between these values is given by Equation 3.

$$\frac{d}{b} = \frac{f}{z} \quad (3)$$

While we know the focal length of the camera, there is no baseline measure in a monocular video. Therefore, we cannot have an accurate notion of scale in a video captured by a monocular camera. Hence, for the rest of this paper, we assume that $b = 1$. Using the MonoDepth network’s disparity output, we calculate z for each pixel of the image.

To verify whether a pixel represents an obstacle or not, we perform ground estimation following the method described in [6], assuming fixed pitch and roll angles. By having an estimate of the depth of the ground plane z_g , we can assume that pixels with depth $z < z_g + \theta$ are above the ground and should be considered obstacles. θ is a threshold we use to make sure we do not consider most of the noise in the ground depth to be an obstacle.

To determine whether an area in the frame is free or obstructed, we merge the results of both obstacle detection and depth estimation. Let $c_{object} \in [0, 1]$ represent the cost of a pixel as a function of nearby objects detected by our neural network, and let $c_{obstacle} \in [0, 1]$ represent the cost of a pixel as a function of obstacles detected using ground and depth estimation. We generate a cost map, where each pixel of a frame has an associated cost c , with values $c \in [0, 1]$, which is given by $c = \max(c_{object}, c_{obstacle})$. Lower cost values indicate a higher chance of the area represented by the pixel being unoccupied, while higher values indicate that the area is likely to represent an obstruction. To do this, we localize which pixels in the image are inside the bounding box of an object detected with

the object detection neural network and attribute $c_{object} = 1$ to pixels inside that bounding box. Pixels surrounding the bounding box represent areas near the obstacle, which the pedestrian will avoid, so we attribute a value $c_{object} \neq 0$, which decreases linearly with the distance to the object. All other pixels have value $c_{object} = 0$. Similarly, if we consider that a pixel does not belong to the ground plane, we attribute a cost $c_{obstacle} = 1$ to it.

We show an example of the cost calculation for a given frame in Figure 1. Using the original frame as input, we get the bounding boxes of objects detected by our object detection network (drawn in red in the figure), including most of the cars in the original frame and one pedestrian. We use this information to calculate the object cost c_{object} for each pixel of the frame. Using the disparity estimate, we calculate the obstacle cost $c_{obstacle}$ to discriminate obstacles that might not have been detected by the object detection network. In this particular example, we were able to identify the lamp post. However, some areas were considered to be obstacles, even though they are not. We believe this derives from the noise of the disparity estimate and from not considering the camera’s pitch and roll angles in our ground plane estimation method. After these intermediate steps, we calculate the total cost c of each pixel, which reveals what areas of the frame are plausibly free for the pedestrian to occupy and which the pedestrian will probably avoid.

3.3 3D Mapping

Using the depth map obtained from the disparity information, we can retrieve the estimated 3D position (x, y, z) in the camera reference frame of a location represented by a pixel. We calculate x and y according to Equation 4, where (c_x, c_y) is the camera’s principal point offset and f_x and f_y are the horizontal and vertical focal lengths, respectively, which we consider to be the same and equal to f .

$$x = \frac{(u - c_x) * z}{f_x}, \quad y = \frac{(v - c_y) * z}{f_y} \quad (4)$$

In an image with w pixels of width and h pixels of height, we obtain a point cloud with $w * h$ points, essentially mapping every pixel in the 2D image to a 3D point in the camera’s reference frame, as shown in Figure 2.

Now that we can map each pixel to a 3D position, we can associate each pixel’s cost in our cost map to a 3D position in the camera’s frame of reference. Because working with a point cloud is difficult, we average the cost over the vertical axis of the camera reference plane to obtain a 2D image of the costs, from a “top-down” perspective, as shown in Figure 3.

The 2D cost image provides essential information regarding the pedestrian’s surroundings. Namely, which areas are free for pedestrians to move and what obstacles are visible to the pedestrians. By integrating our knowledge about each pixel’s depth, we can extract more data regarding the pedestrian’s surroundings and better estimate its behavior. For instance, from Figure 3 we can predict that

Fig. 1. Calculation of pixel cost through object and obstacle detection.

Fig. 2. Point cloud generated mapping pixels to 3D points using the estimated disparity information.

Fig. 3. Mapping of cost from image to the camera reference frame. To facilitate visualization, the cost has been averaged along the vertical axis, providing a “top-down” view.

the pedestrian will unlikely move straight forward, as that area has a high cost. Actually, during the next frames, the pedestrian moves to the left, avoiding the lamp post.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we describe how we processed video captured from a monocular camera worn by a pedestrian to create a map of the pedestrian’s surroundings, identifying possible obstacles and open areas. We trained and utilized two networks: one for object detection and another for disparity estimation. Using data from both, we are able to associate a cost and a 3D position to each pixel in video frames. Using this map, we take a step towards understanding a pedestrian’s environment, which is essential to comprehend what influences the actions taken by these road users.

Future work involves adding tracking detected objects and estimating the change of pose of the camera between frames using monocular odometry techniques, so that we may infer the pedestrian’s position in the real world. Using the resulting trajectory, we can combine the cost maps of each frame to generate a unique cost map for each video, and we can perceive the pedestrian’s actions and associate them with the environment, which should enable us to better understand behavior.

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